

CLASSIFICATION OF MODERN FACILITIES USED IN THE STORAGE OF COTTON FIBER AT THE "BEK CLUSTER" ENTERPRISE. SCIENTIFIC SUBSTANTIATION OF THE EFFECT OF MOISTURE ON FIBER QUALITY DURING THE STORAGE OF COTTON RAW MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

In the storage of cotton raw materials, modern equipment is of great importance. This article is about the modern technologies used in the cotton ginning plant of JV "Bek cluster" established in the Mirzaabad district of the Sirdarya region, the effect of moisture on the fiber quality during cotton processing.

КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ МОЩНОСТЕЙ, ИСПОЛЪЗУЕМЫХ ПРИ ХРАНЕНИИ ХЛОПКОВОГО ВОЛОКНА НА ПРЕДПРИЯТИИ «БЕК КЛАСТЕР». НАУЧНОЕ ОБОСНОВАНИЕ ВЛИЯНИЯ ВЛАГИ НА КАЧЕСТВО ВОЛОКНА ПРИ ХРАНЕНИИ ХЛОПКОВОГО СЫРЬЯ

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ABSTRACT

При хранении хлопкового сырья большое значение имеет современное оборудование. В данной статье речь идет о современных технологиях, используемых на хлопкоочистительном заводе СП «Бек кластер», созданном в Мирзаабадском районе Сырдарьинской области, влиянии влаги на качество волокна при переработке хлопка.

Cotton is received and stored separately according to selection, industrial varieties and picking methods in cotton processing facilities and cotton ginning enterprises.

Collection of cotton bunches, their storage and processing is carried out separately for each farm, according to the type of fiber, taking into account its quality indicators, following the "Cotton picking and preparation instructions".

Seed cotton is received and collected in separate bunches from technical cotton.

Cotton infected with various pests and diseases ("black aphid", gommosis, macrosporiosis, etc.) is received separately, collected, stored and sent for processing.

In order to store cotton better and organize long-term storage, it is necessary to collect cotton in layers, taking into account its moisture content. Cotton with a moisture content of up to 14% should be placed in the area of the cleaning department, and cotton with a moisture content of 14% and above should be placed in the area of the dry-cleaning shop. Cotton with a moisture content of more than 20 percent should be stored close to the drying room, as it needs to be quickly dried and processed.

Closed warehouses, semi-open or four-sided warehouses (porches) and open specially prepared areas are used for cotton storage.

It is allowed to collect cotton in the areas covered with gravel or asphalt. The middle should be raised by 0.05-0.07 m.

Cotton of low quality, dirtiness and high humidity is placed in a special small jar. The length of such a gharam is 14 m, width 7 m, height 4.0-4.5 m (the rectangular part is 3.1 m, the height of the domed part is 1.5 m). In one 14 x 25 m standard garam area, three such garams are placed.

After placing each layer of cotton 1 m high, the edges of the gharam are plastered not less than 0.5 m. The corners of the garden are more densely plastered with a width of 2.5-3.0 m. It is recommended to place no more than 80 tons of cotton per day.

When placing the cotton in the bins, its side walls rise due to its subsidence, and it is necessary to comb them.

The maximum height of the walls of the cave is 7.5 m, the conical part on the top of the cave is dome-shaped and should not exceed 2.5 m. The center of the conical part should pass through the middle of the cone lengthwise.

Tarpaulin tents measuring 8.5 x 7 m are used to cover the cotton fields. The 25 x 14 m gharam is covered with ten tarpaulins. The tarpaulins are sewn in pairs to form a tent with 7 m x 17 m sides, and when it is necessary to cover the 25 x 14 m gharam with 8 tarpaulins, they are made in pairs with 7 m sides. Then the formed tents are sewn again in pairs with sides of 17 m. Two such tarpaulins are closed to the gharam with a side of 17 m across so that the second tarpaulin protrudes 1 m above the first one.

The tarpaulin is pulled by a rope through its rings. The ends of the ropes are tied to the wire rings placed on the ground around the gharam. The tarpaulin covering the bag should cover no less than 350-400 tons of cotton.

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